
“SYNCHRONOUS” IN SCIENCE EDUCATION – THE NEED, THE OPPORTUNITY AND THE PRACTICE

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The problem

Asynchronous methods have been dominating the Distance Learning (DL) panorama for many years and even now, despite the widespread of more interactive technologies and the need for better and more interactive tools, asynchronous interaction, mostly via forum/message boards and Web content, is frequently the “solo” formula adopted in eLearning courses and *content* quality is still the big issue.

The need

Far from being a perfect form of communication, the “all asynchronous” practice is often a consequence of inadequate synchronous solutions and a poor integration in the course goals; therefore new approaches for asynchronous/synchronous integration are needed.

In science education we have experienced that communicating through forum is too slow, inaccurate and largely insufficient, especially when problem solving and the modern investigative strategies are adopted.

Either in face-to-face teaching or in distance teaching is important to create constructivist learning environments, if our intention is the *meaningful learning* of the students, and synchronous methods contribute to promote those kind of learning environments.

The opportunity

Benefiting from a new philosophy of asynchronous and synchronous integration, available in the Odisseia Platform, we had the opportunity to adopt a more interactive DL approach including synchronous and multiuser tools (2D and 3D) in the mix strategy of our courses.

The practice: from content to pedagogical communication

We illustrate examples of such integration in our courses using the Odisseia platform that show how, although *content* materials remain important, we are moving the focus more and more from content to *communication* in DL educative practice.

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The "all asynchronous" eLearning model: a biased practice

Texts, videos, CD-ROM, etc., distributed by post mail or TV broadcast in the previous models of distance learning (DL) have been gradually replaced by Web sites and e-Learning platform systems. Besides asynchronous availability of materials, asynchronous communication by way of message boards (forum) and email has been widely defended^[1] and become the dominant practice in most distance learning courses (Cardoso, 2007) leading to an unprecedented widespread of a biased practice: the "all asynchronous"

Nothing is wrong with asynchronous methods; they are used for quite long, have their place among other methods and are adequate to some learning styles (Higgison, 2002). The problem is with the "All Asynchronous", which seems to be a dominant practice in most e-Learning courses and surely a bad practice in some cases. Although an improvement in DL, modern asynchronous still are very slow and cumbersome forms of communication, especially if you compare with the "highly interactive and adaptable educational transaction" (Garrison, 2000) that is possible in face-to-face education (F2F). In day to day practice of DL science education (and not exclusively), we have always felt the need for a more dynamic, interactive and rich communication environment which includes both asynchronous and synchronous forms of educational communication.

Old approaches perpetuate old problems: communication

It has been proclaimed for decades, since the old days of DL, that the asynchronous model is more convenient because of the "anytime, anywhere" availability argument. For this concern nothing has really changed in the essence of modern e-learning strategy, so ... most of the old problems^[2] remain and, among them, the *difficulties in communication*.

The asynchronous model of e-learning was promoted by Web's success and follows closely the traditional "long ago proved" Distance Education model and its theoretical foundations, with natural reshaping due to technology evolution and some novelties. One of these crucial novelties is the *forum*. Although we can look at email as a natural and direct substitute for traditional mail we must notice that newsgroups/forums are a new kind of tool in use and probably the most important improvement brought by the asynchronous model (Cardoso, 2005).

Without forums the eLearning phenomena would probably not have happened, but it is far from being a perfect communication tool. In science education eLearning courses we have experienced that communicating trough forum is too slow, inaccurate and largely insufficient^[3], especially when problem solving and the modern investigative strategies are adopted.

Asynchronous difficulties with problem solving eLearning strategies

The asynchronous model tries to address collaboration which is an important component of the educational process but this goal is not favoured by the lack of immediacy of this kind of communication. Socialization is also not favoured enough by asynchronous as many authors have pointed.

In science education (and not only) *problem solving* is a very important strategy. Sometimes students have doubts about particular aspects of the *problems* and in many cases to "solve" the problem, with the tutor or among colleagues, a dynamic, rich and highly interactive kind of communication is needed. In the old days of DL students used to call the educator by telephone. Now, according to the "all asynchronous" model, they have to go trough the slow process of interacting in a written form trough a message board. It's hardly a better solution: "Lack of immediacy still makes it difficult for students to connect quickly with each other or their instructors. Research indicates that this isolation can be a serious detriment to learning (Galusha, 1997; Hara & Khling, 1999; Kubala, 1998; Lockett, 1998)", cited by Schullo (2003).

Figure 1. Discussing in real time, within a virtual class a concept map produced by a group of students (in the Odisseia eLearning platform, developed at Universidade Aberta)

It is important to produce constructivist and investigative learning environments

Either in face-to-face teaching or in distance teaching, *constructivist learning environments* are very important if our intention is the meaningful learning of the students.

As Novak and Gowin say (1999, p. 36), meaningful learning "is an activity which can't be shared; it is actually a question of individual responsibility. Indeed, "on the contrary, meanings can be shared, discussed, negotiated". And more: "learning the meaning of a piece of knowledge requires dialog, exchange, sharing and sometimes compromise."

In other words, although learning is an individual and idiosyncratic process, it can be very influenced by the environment where students work. Thanks to the good interaction and help from both his teacher and mates, each student can very successfully work or perform a task which he would not be able to do if he worked individually. By interacting and collaborating, students will be changing their knowledge schemes and their meanings as they are reaching a greater and greater autonomy and the power to use their own thinking schemes in the face of new and more and more complex situations and tasks (Vygotsky, 1991).

Learning must definitely be accepted as every student's personal and idiosyncratic activity and he must be given controlled freedom and shared responsibility to learn in a stimulating environment of permanent dialogue and cooperation, being the teacher a supporting and facilitating agent, a fundamental mediator (Valadares, 2001, p. 12). Such stimulating environment is a constructivist and investigative learning environment.

Although since the third decade of last century many works proved that the behaviour of a student is a function of himself and of the environment where he works, the systematic research on learning environments begun in the sixth decade with the pioneer works of Herbert Walberg and Rudolf Moos (Sebela, 2003; Fraser, 2006).

For these last five decades, several works were developed and the last ones incorporating modern constructivist ideas about knowledge and recent ideas about investigative methods of teaching and learning.

Figure 2. A synchronous Math lesson using Chat and synchronous whiteboard (Odiseia platform, Universidade Aberta)

A constructivist learning environment is, according to Wilson (1996, in Jonassen et al., 1999, p. 194), "a place where learners work together and support each other as they are using a variety of tools and sources of information, following the orientation of the learning purposes and the activities of problem solving." These activities must enclose experiences under multiple perspectives, to provide realistic and excellent contexts, to stimulate the contribution of the students and the assuming of responsibilities for their processes of learning, must also provide multiple forms of representation of the involved situations in the learning and to imply the students be conscientious of the proper process of knowledge construction, through reflexive and metacognitive activities (Cunningham, Duffy and Knuth, 1993).

Building such an environment is not only the teacher's exclusive responsibility but it has a lot to do with the way the teacher faces teaching and learning, and the tools he uses.

Synchronous methods contribute to promote constructivist learning environments

In a constructivist learning environment (Brooks & Brooks, 1999):

- questioning and listening to students is considered important;
- curricular activities are essentially based on primary data and information sources and manipulative materials;
- students are considered like thinkers who have personal representations of the world they live in;
- generically, teachers interact with their students, worrying about their learning environment;
- teachers look for their students' viewpoints with the purpose of understanding their conceptions to explore them in their learning;
- evaluating learning is diversified and a part of teaching, based on observing the students' activity systematically and the work they do;
- students work essentially in groups, communicating as much as possible amongst them.

These environments, being important for face-to-face education, acquire as much or bigger importance in the context of distance education, particularly when we design lessons and choose the tools of learning, using the modern technologies. It was also thinking about distance teaching that Savery and Duffy (1995) establish four principles that will have to be emphasized:

1. The learning is an active and involving process.
2. The learning is a process of knowledge construction.
3. The learners will have to "function" in a metacognitive level.
4. The learning will have to involve "social negotiation".

Clarifying the third principle, these authors affirm that the learning must not only be focused in capacities of thinking and in arriving at "the certain" answers, as it occurred in the traditional activities of routine. The students will have to prepare their proper strategies trying to go ahead to the resolutions of problems and to become more and more autonomous based on the capacity of reflection.

Figure 3. Working in a 3D virtual lab with synchronous support from tutors and interaction with colleagues (in the Odisseia platform, developed at Universidade Aberta)

Concerning the fourth principle, the students will have to be capable to think about their thinking, beliefs, perceptions and knowledge in contribution with the colleagues. This involves an easy communication amongst students and synchronous tools facilitate them. Many DL educators ignore synchronous in their relation with students but tools like messengers (with only text or including voice or video) are already very popular among students and used discuss study subjects and group work.

In order to "function" in a metacognitive level and to participate in "social negotiation", students must use metacognitive tools, and negotiate ideas based on them, more easily if they use synchronous tools.

Examples where synchronous communication is an advantage

As good examples of metacognitive tools we can refer the concept maps of Novak and Vee diagrams of Gowin. These tools help each student to learn better and better and to know more and more the nature of producing/building knowledge (Novak and Gowin, 1999; Moreira and Buchweitz, 1993).

Figure 4. A virtual study visit to the fauna and flora of Bird's Island, Seychelles (a multiuser 3D environment, Odisseia platform)

Concept mapping is a technique that exposes the concepts and assertions hidden within the cognitive structure of each student and it is of great importance since it shows the changes occurring in this cognitive structure, clarifies misconceptions and superficial interpretation in the teaching/learning process, and allows the teacher and student to exchange points of view on the validity or absence of a link between two concepts. In addition, the process of creating

concept maps may also contribute to the development of a cooperation between the student and teacher in the sharing of meaning, where "making and remaking concept maps, and sharing it with others may be considered a team effort in the sport of thinking" (Novak, 1990a).

The importance of the concept map role in science teaching has been demonstrated since the publication, in 1990, of a special edition of the *Journal of Research in Science Teaching* about this subject that includes an article by Al-Kunified & Wandersee (1990) citing around one hundred references related to the use of the maps. Since then, considerable research has validated the usefulness of concept maps in meaningful learning. Concept maps assist teachers in controlling the students' learning since "they may be used to map out a route for organizing and presenting knowledge to students, as well as for finding students' alternative conceptions" (Novak, 1991, p. 38). It is also important that they become excellent tools in helping the student control his own learning. Actually, besides helping in building new knowledge and learning key concepts, concept maps will help the student with learning how to learn (Novak and Gowin, 1999).

A good strategy to explore concept maps in DL is to discuss, in real time, within a virtual class a concept map produced by a group of students (Figure 1). In figure 1 we show a very simple use of plain chat. But a better and richer interaction is possible, in *the Odisseia eLearning platform*, developed by Cardoso (2005) has shown here, with the complementary use of synchronous whiteboard. Alternatively we could use *CmapTools* from IHMC (Institute for Human and Machine Cognition). It permits students to construct, navigate, share and criticize ideas represented as concept maps. Each student or group of students can construct a Cmap in a computer and share it on servers (CmapServers) anywhere on the Internet. This discussion of concept maps can be developed in an asynchronous way but can be better explored if students can also communicate through a chat, for example.

Other good examples of useful synchronous support and interaction we have been working with are problem solving and synchronous sessions (Figure 2) with or without the support of multiuser Whiteboards, virtual lab sessions (Figure 3) and multiuser 3D environments with avatars for virtual study visits (Figure 4) among other rich and stimulating online activities made possible by adequate tools and the right educational strategy.

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- [1] Some reference personalities of on-line education like Murray Goldberg (of WebCT fame) clearly position themselves in the side of the Asynchronous model, questioning the usefulness of synchronous chats in the learning environment and proclaiming his bias/preference toward, and "almost exclusive use of asynchronous communication tools" in electronic course offerings and not "because of the bandwidth, software or equipment needed for synchronous" (Goldberg, 2003). The use of technology has brought not only better solutions but new problems too, like the usability of computer and multimedia systems.
- [2] The use of technology has brought not only better solutions but new problems too, like the usability of computer and multimedia systems.
- [3] A forum post can be confusing, misinterpreted or remain unanswered, hidden among other messages. Because of the *slowness* some confusing or potential misinterpreted messages are not questioned enough. The user quickly understands that this medium is not adequate for long threads and, sometimes, he may fear that exposing too much doubt in a "written" and "persistent" form of communication can be misunderstood with lack of study and have impact on grades.

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